

MODEL OF THE BALL-TRACING ROBOT

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Model of the simple ball-following robot is presented. The robot with a camera follows a white ping-pong ball, trying to hold its position in the centre of the camera image. Using the classical control theory we try to explain and predict the behaviour of the mobile robot controlled by an agent-space architecture controller. Some problems with different control algorithms are described, design of the simple feedback proportional controller is compared with the agent-space architecture. With such simple model of the robot we can successfully describe its behaviour and moreover we can predict its changes depending on parameter modification.

Key words: mobile robot, agent-space architecture, control system, proportional gain, time delay

INTRODUCTION

In the article [1] its author describes a mobile robot with a camera, following a ping-pong ball. The robot travels on a black surface and the ball is in contrast white. Nothing else can be found in the area. As the mobile platform was used an educational robot Boe-Bot (see Fig. 1) and a wireless camera Xcam2. The image processing and all the computations are performed remotely on the workstation computer, commands are transferred using the wireless communication established between the robot and the workstation.

Figure 1. Boe-Bot robot with the camera

Author describes the control algorithm for the robot using the *agent-space architecture*. This control architecture consists of independent building blocks communicating over common data areas. The whole controller consists of independent agents, each of them working at the implicit sampling times. Such an architecture enables easy modification of the controller, simply by adding more agents operating on the same data space.

Figure 2. Agent-space architecture [1]

Such a control system follows the ball successfully, although in [2] are mentioned some problems. The robot sometimes oscillates, movement is not fluent and stable. The agent-space architecture can't explain this behaviour, so we create the model of the robot and analyse its' behaviour.

MODEL OF THE SYSTEM

The robot control algorithm can be separated into the two (relatively) independent processes. The goal of the first

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one is to move towards the ball, i.e. to hold the ball position in the centre of the camera image. The goal of the second one is to hold the distance from the ball, i.e. the size of the ball in the camera image. Next we describe the positioning of the robot towards the ball. We introduce an one-dimensional coordinate system, with a centre in the middle of the image. The deviations to the right are positive, to the left negative (see Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Image from the camera

Although the algorithm for the recognition of the ball in the image consists of many steps including the Sobel image operator, thresholding, thinning and pruning filters, edges detection and finally the Hough transformation, we will consider the camera algorithm as a monolithic block with a single input (scanned ball position) and a single output (measured position).

Figure 4. Model of the camera

Let us suppose that there is just a pure delay T_D between the input and output signals:

$$ball_position(t) = position(t - T_D)$$

Further component of the system is a mobile robot Boe-Bot. At this moment we will consider only the simple rotation of the robot on the place (pivoting), which results in a movement of the ball image in the camera. When we apply a scalable amount of energy to the motors, the robot starts to move. When applying the full range (100%), the robot rotates right. When applying the energy in opposite

direction (-100%), the robot rotates left. And finally, without energy (0%) the robot stops indeed (see Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Model of the robot

The position will increase with time, what leads to a model of the robot as a pure integrator:

$$position(t) = 1/T_M \int motor(t) dt,$$

where T_M (integral time constant) depends on the pivoting speed. Again, at this moment we are not interesting about the internal construction of the robot, we just use its behaviour as the basis for the model.

The last but not least important part of the system is the controller. It is implemented as a piece of a software code, but it is not important. Its task is to calculate the *difference* between the set point (wished position of the ball in the camera image) and the *ball position*. It is clear, that for very small deviation of the ball position it is not necessary to apply the full power to the motors, so we use the *proportional* amount of energy, depending on the size of the *position error*. There is a *negative feedback*, which moves the robot *against* the changes it measures:

$$motor(t) = K_R (setpoint(t) - ball_position(t))$$

The dependency constant K_R between the error and the required action is called a *proportional gain*.

Figure 6. Model of the system

In our case the wished value of the ball position is always zero (i.e. the ball is in the centre of the image), so

the controller's task is not to follow the set point value, but simply to control the position in the cases of random disturbances, represented by the movement of the ball in the outside environment.

SIMULATIONS

At this moment we have enough information about the structure of the whole system to try some simulations. As we did not measure the actual parameters of the system, let us estimate them. We assume the delay between the capture and evaluation of the image to be 0,5 second. Also we assume the speed of the robot rotation at the place to be 3 cm/s.

Table 1. **Simulation parameters**

	T_D	T_M	K_R	Step	Method
Figure 7	0,5 [s]	1/3 [s]	1.20 [-]	0,1 [s]	Ode4
Figure 8	0,5 [s]	1/3 [s]	0.80 [-]	0,1 [s]	Ode4
Figure 9	0,5 [s]	1/3 [s]	1.0472	0,1 [s]	Ode4
Figure 10	0,5 [s]	1/3 [s]	0.20 [-]	0,1 [s]	Ode4
Figure 11	0,1 [s]	1/3 [s]	1.20 [-]	0,1 [s]	Ode4

Figure 7. **Ball position step change (red) and the robot response (blue). $K_R=1,20$**

At this moment we can try some simulations of the system behaviour when the ball at certain moment moves from steady position to another one. This is modelled as the disturbance. The response of the system for different values of the controller proportional gain are on the Fig. 7 and 8.

Figure 8. **Ball position step change (red) and the robot response (green). $K_R=0,80$**

Simulations show that behaviour of the system perfectly matches those described in [2]. Now we should ask, if we are able to predict something more, based on the information about our model.

ANALYSIS

It is possible to create the transfer function between the disturbance and resulting position of the robot. After the Laplace transformation of the model and some block manipulations from the Fig. 6. we obtain following equation

$$Y(s) = W(s) \frac{K}{s + K e^{-sT_D}}$$

where $K = K_R / T_M$, and $W(s)$ is the transfer function of the disturbance. Unfortunately, due to the exponential member (time lag) we are not able to find exact solution using the inverse Laplace transformation. But if we are satisfied with the first order Padé approximation [3]

$$e^{-sT_D} = \frac{a - s}{a + s}, \text{ where } a = \frac{2}{T_D}$$

then we obtain the following response of the system to the step change of the disturbance ($W(s)=1/s$)

$$Y(s) = \frac{sK + \frac{2K}{T_D}}{s^3 + s_2(\frac{2}{T_D} - K) + s\frac{2K}{T_D}}$$

with the following solution for $t \geq 0$, which can be found using the inverse Laplace transform

$$y(t) = 1 - \frac{\sqrt{(\alpha - a)^2 + b^2}}{b} e^{-at} \sin(bt + \phi),$$

where

$$\alpha = 2\left(\frac{K_R}{T_M} - \frac{1}{T_D}\right)$$

$$a = \frac{1}{T_D} - \frac{K_R}{2T_M}$$

$$b^2 = \frac{3K_R}{T_M T_D} - \frac{K_R^2}{4T_M^2} - \frac{1}{T_D^2}$$

Using these results, one can find the critical gain. We search for such value of the K_R that system will perform stable oscillations. We can find it as a solution of the characteristic equation

$$1 + \frac{K_R e^{-sT_D}}{sT_M} = 0$$

which gives

$$K_R = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{T_M}{T_D}$$

and for values from the simulation example we obtain $K_R = 1,0472$, which gives the following simulation results (see Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Response of the robot to the position step change (pink) for $K_R=1,0472$

Moreover, we are able to improve the robot behaviour finding such value of the proportional gain, that its movement is stable and without overshoots (see Fig. 10).

Figure 10. Response of the robot to the position step change (green) for $K_R=0,8$

Another possibility how to improve the robot behaviour requires significant technical change – if we are able to update images from the camera more quickly, let say at each 0,1 seconds, then the time delay will not play a significant role in the system. The control process will be stable even for higher values of the gain (see Fig. 11).

Figure 11. Response of the robot to the position step change (magenta) for $K_R=1,20$ and reduced camera time $T_D=0,1$

SIMPLIFICATIONS

We didn't mention some simplifications that we use through the text.

First one is the fact that we analysed just left-right, and not forward-backward movements. Even when considering the constant distance L between the ball and robot, we consider the movement linear even that rotating robot requires movement of the ball on the circle (see Fig. 12). We can assume such a distance L that the difference is small enough.

Figure 12. Ball following (top view)

Next, the model of the robot assumes pure integrator, which reacts on the signal immediately. This is not real, as the robot has certain inertia mass m that delays the responses. The mass of the robot with batteries and camera is about 500 grams, so comparing it with its relatively slow movements, we can neglect it.

Further, in a real robot, the dependence of the movement on the input signal to the motor is not linear as we quietly assumed. Moreover, the motor power is not unlimited, so we cannot go over the certain limits. Again, we can neglect this problem for relatively small deviations around the stable position near zero.

The main difference between the model and the real robot is in the camera processing model. In reality, the captured image has not the same properties and its analysis depends on many factors. One can easily imagine that the ball recognition takes much more time when more objects are detected in the image. Each image processing time (modelled with the time delay T_D) takes variable time amount. We can bypass this problem taking only the largest value of T_D into account. The real robot will not show the regular oscillations, but each one has slightly different period. This can be avoided using as uniform environmental conditions as possible.

CONCLUSIONS

Even the artificial intelligence methods are supposed to be “more clever” than the standard approaches, in our example the classical approach gives more than only description of the system. We obtain also an ability to predict the behaviour of the system and to find a precise values of the critical system parameters.

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